

to the dissociation of phenolic OH and pK_2 corresponding to the association of proton to azomethine nitrogen were determined at $\bar{n}_A=0.5$ and 1.5, respectively. From the titration curves, \bar{n} and pL values were also computed for metal-ligand systems and from \bar{n} vs pL curves, (Fig. 2) $\log K_1$ values for various metal complexes were determined by half integral method. All the values

Fig. 1. Formation curve of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-(4''-morpholinyl)aniline.

Fig. 2. Metal-ligand systems of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-(4''-morpholinyl)aniline.

were further corroborated by the straight line plots of $\log (\bar{n}/1-\bar{n})$ vs pL . The most representative values are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1

	$t=30^\circ$			$\mu=0.1 M$			
	H ⁺	Y ³⁺	Pr ³⁺	Nd ³⁺	Sm ³⁺	Gd ³⁺	Dy ³⁺
$\log K_1$	10.34	8.06	8.25	8.02	7.48	7.52	7.72
$\log K_2$	4.35	—	—	—	—	—	—

The order of stability of metal chelates is found to be $Pr^{3+} > Y^{3+} > Nd^{3+} > Dy^{3+} > Gd^{3+} > Sm^{3+}$.

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Viscosity of Glycine in Alcohol-Water Mixtures at 308.15 K

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VISCOSITY and volumetric studies have been reported on amino acids in aqueous solutions¹⁻⁴. These measurements can be all the more interesting if made in mixed solvents containing water. The viscosity and volumetric studies of amino acids in solvents other than water do not appear to have been made except in water + dimethyl formamide⁵. There has been considerable interest in aqueous solutions of the lower aliphatic alcohols because of their unique structural relationship to pure water⁶. The viscosities and densities of glycine in alcohol + water mixtures containing up to 25% (w/w) of alcohol have, therefore, been measured over a range of concentrations at 308.15 K. The alcohols studied are methanol, ethanol, *n*-propanol and *t*-butanol. The data are used to calculate the viscosity B- and D- coefficients.

Experimental

Methods of purification of methanol (BDH, AR), ethanol (Bengal Chemical), *n*-propanol (Riedel, AR) and *t*-butanol (S. Merck, LR) were the same as described by Vogel⁷. Purified liquids were stored in well stoppered bottles and were distilled afresh before use. Glycine (extra pure grade) was obtained from E. Merck and was used without further purification except drying in an oven at 403 K for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. It was stored over anhydrous calcium oxide in a vacuum desiccator.

Solutions were prepared on molar basis in double distilled water and vacuum corrections were applied to all weighings.

Ubbelohde type⁸ capillary viscometer was used for viscosity measurements. The accuracy in time

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of flow was ± 0.1 sec. Kinetic energy correction was applied to the viscosity data and accuracy was found to be ± 3 parts in 10^4 . The densities were determined with single stem pycnometer having a volume of 14 cm^3 , accuracy being ± 2 parts in 10^4 .

Results and Discussion

The densities and relative viscosities of glycine solutions in 5, 15 and 25% (w/w) alcohol + water mixtures at 308.15 K and at different concentrations are given in Table 1. The variation of relative viscosity (η/η_0) with concentration, C, is expressed by Jones-Dole equation

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + BC + DC^2 \quad \dots (1)$$

TABLE 1—DENSITY, ρ , AND RELATIVE VISCOSITY, η/η_0 , VALUES AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS AND AT 308.15 K

C/mol dm ⁻³	$\rho/\text{g cm}^{-3}$	η/η_0
Glycine in 5% w/w methanol + water $\rho_0 = 0.98653 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$; $\eta_0 = 814.6 \times 10^{-6}$ poise		
0.01894	0.98739	1.00147
0.07086	0.98984	1.01166
0.21766	0.99538	1.03670
0.32711	1.00126	1.05880
0.47278	1.00805	1.08630
Glycine in 15% w/w methanol + water $\rho_0 = 0.96987 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$; $\eta_0 = 974.5 \times 10^{-6}$ poise		
0.07447	0.97321	1.01954
0.14636	0.97671	1.03346
0.26899	0.98212	1.05478
0.32924	0.98541	1.06860
0.48698	0.99399	1.10468
Glycine in 25% w/w methanol + water $\rho_0 = 0.95319 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$; $\eta_0 = 1122.4 \times 10^{-6}$ poise		
0.06109	0.95665	1.01046
0.14898	0.96031	1.02690
0.25378	0.96685	1.04988
0.34075	0.97064	1.07005
0.46868	0.97963	1.09201
Glycine in 5% w/w ethanol + water $\rho_0 = 0.98711 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$; $\eta_0 = 825.8 \times 10^{-6}$ poise		
0.06552	0.99027	1.00745
0.15727	0.99604	1.02758
0.26269	1.00106	1.04441
0.34639	1.00584	1.06417
0.47184	1.01169	1.08956
Glycine in 15% w/w ethanol + water $\rho_0 = 0.97600 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$; $\eta_0 = 1002.4 \times 10^{-6}$ poise		
0.07076	0.97979	1.01692
0.07187	0.97999	1.02118
0.15525	0.98485	1.02858
0.25856	0.98892	1.04570
0.34512	0.99442	1.06416
0.47780	1.00108	1.09380
Glycine in 25% w/w ethanol + water $\rho_0 = 0.95972 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$; $\eta_0 = 1328.2 \times 10^{-6}$ poise		
0.06999	0.96400	1.01341
0.15184	0.96724	1.03077
0.25642	0.97283	1.04860
0.33894	0.97600	1.06632
0.47027	0.98167	1.09032

Glycine in 5% w/w <i>n</i> -propanol + water $\rho_0 = 0.98678 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$; $\eta_0 = 856.0 \times 10^{-6}$ poise		
0.07181	0.98883	1.00686
0.15622	0.99225	1.02439
0.26246	0.99567	1.03997
0.34745	0.99925	1.05718
0.48802	1.00452	1.07265
Glycine in 15% w/w <i>n</i> -propanol + water $\rho_0 = 0.97131 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$; $\eta_0 = 1163.0 \times 10^{-6}$ poise		
0.07106	0.97386	1.01182
0.07131	0.97394	1.01290
0.15441	0.97747	1.02568
0.26263	0.98092	1.03919
0.34265	0.98491	1.05197
0.47571	0.98863	1.07361
Glycine in 25% w/w <i>n</i> -propanol + water $\rho_0 = 0.95490 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$; $\eta_0 = 1442.8 \times 10^{-6}$ poise		
0.07058	0.95597	1.01254
0.15132	0.95786	1.03409
0.25214	0.96023	1.04784
0.33564	0.96411	1.06350
0.46601	0.96752	1.08442
Glycine in 5% w/w <i>t</i> -butanol + water $\rho_0 = 0.98607 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$; $\eta_0 = 879.3 \times 10^{-6}$ poise		
0.07274	0.98844	1.01254
0.07354	0.98840	1.01782
0.15677	0.99196	1.02716
0.26182	0.99532	1.03800
0.35423	0.99895	1.05322
0.49026	1.00256	1.07963
Glycine in 15% w/w <i>t</i> -butanol + water $\rho_0 = 0.97252 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$; $\eta_0 = 1328.9 \times 10^{-6}$ poise		
0.07237	0.97409	1.00531
0.15412	0.97621	1.02235
0.25796	0.98023	1.03829
0.34300	0.98348	1.04910
0.47306	0.98735	1.07311
Glycine in 25% w/w <i>t</i> -butanol + water $\rho_0 = 0.95157 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$; $\eta_0 = 1816.5 \times 10^{-6}$ poise		
0.07091	0.95304	1.01200
0.15138	0.95705	1.02112
0.25318	0.96144	1.03526
0.33661	0.96422	1.04536
0.46335	0.96773	1.05789

where η is the viscosity of solution and η_0 is the viscosity of the solvent, B and D are empirical coefficients. The values of B and D coefficients have been obtained from equation (1) by plotting $(\eta/\eta_0 - 1)/C$ vs C. The intercepts and slopes of straight line plots yield viscosity B and D coefficients given in Table 2. Coefficient B measures the size and shape effect of the solute as well as the structural effects induced by solute-solvent interactions; the significance of D, however, is still obscure⁹. A survey of the data reveals the following.

(i) It can be seen from Table 1 that the viscosity of alcohol + water mixtures increases with increasing amount of the alcohol in the mixture. Such effects in ethanol + water mixtures have been

TABLE 2—THE η_{sp}/c AND D COEFFICIENT VALUES FOR GLYCINE AT 308.15 K IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Solvent	$B/\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	$D/\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-2}$
5% methanol	0.164	0.0947
15% methanol	0.207	0.0545
25% methanol	0.173	0.1700
5% ethanol	0.168	0.1702
15% ethanol	0.182	0.0645
25% ethanol	0.192	0.0200
5% <i>n</i> -propanol	0.158	-0.0645
15% <i>n</i> -propanol	0.168	-0.1429
25% <i>n</i> -propanol	0.174	0.2143
5% <i>t</i> -butanol	0.126	0.3654
15% <i>t</i> -butanol	0.141	0.1290
25% <i>t</i> -butanol	0.157	-0.3529

attributed^{10,11} to the fact that addition of small amount of ethanol in water enhances the structure of water resulting in a more structured solvent. With this observation we shall assume that the increase in viscosity with addition of alcohol to water up to 25% w/w of alcohol is due to the successive enhancement of structure in the solvent mixtures.

(ii) In Table 2 the B coefficients of glycine show increase with increase in percentage of alcohol in the solvent mixtures. It is also known from previous studies² that glycine in water solutions having high B coefficients acts as a net structure breaker. Using the above description of glycine in water, the increase in B coefficients support the interpretation that glycine is even more effective as a structure breaker in alcohol-water mixtures than in water. The increased structure breaking by glycine in the mixed solvent is probably due to the already enhanced structure in the original solvent mixtures.

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Influence of Dipolar Aprotic Solvents on Micellization of Aqueous Solution of Surfactants. Part—I: A Study of Micellization of Surfactants in $\text{H}_2\text{O-N,N-Dimethyl Formamide}$ Solution

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MICELLIZATION studies in aquo-organic solvent systems have largely been restricted to protic solvents like alcohols and aprotic water soluble solvents like dioxane. Some workers have used acetone and various amides as cosolvents to study their effect on cmc's. McDonald¹ observed substantially higher values of cmc's for nonionic surfactants in formamide and lower values for some sodium carboxylates both in formamide and N-methyl acetamide. Gopal and coworkers²⁻⁴ reported aggregation of ionic surfactants in solvents having one hydrogen bonding centre, like *n*-methyl acetamide. This paper considers the effect of N,N-dimethyl formamide, a dipolar aprotic solvent having no hydrogen bonding centre, on the cmc's of CTAB, NaLS and Triton-X-100.

Experimental

N,N-Dimethyl formamide (DMF) was of spectrograde (E. Merck) and used without further purification. The surfactants used in this study were cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB), sodium lauryl sulphate (NaLS), both of BDH make and used after purification⁵. Polyoxyethylene-9,5-diisobutyl phenol (Triton-X-100) was of BDH make and used without further purification. The dye used was methyl violet (E. Merck) [$\lambda_{\text{max}}=580$ nm and $\epsilon_{\text{max}}=25,000$]. All solutions were prepared in double distilled water and preserved in "Corning" glass apparatus in the dark to avoid any photochemical reaction, and used within 7 days of preparation.

All measurements were carried out spectroscopically using a Carl Zeiss VSU-2P spectrophotometer containing thermostated cell holders. The solutions required for experiment were bottled and shaken thoroughly for 2 hr to ensure complete incorporation. The bottles were then kept in the thermostat for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hr to attain temperature equilibrium. Change of optical densities were followed at the maximum absorption, of the dye i.e. at 580 nm in aqueous and mixed solvent systems, in varying concentrations of the surfactants, and at a fixed dye concentration (1×10^{-5} M). Each value reported is an average of 3 readings. From the plots of O. D. vs concentration of surfactant, the